

Aerodynamic optimization of freight-train operation: utilizing real-world and wind-tunnel experiments

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Abstract

The DLR FR8-LAB, a self-contained measurement-system equipped container has been used to take aerodynamic measurements on operational freight-trains. Transient pressure was measured with 330 sensors, and the global transient-forces and moments have been derived: aerodynamic drag – important for operational efficiency, and side-force and rolling moment – important for safety (the risk of overturning and derailment). LiDAR sensors, satellite navigation and thermal cameras are used to couple the aerodynamic measurements with the operating scenarios. Results have indicated significant differences in aerodynamic characteristics based on the operating conditions of freight trains: loading configuration, tunnels, crosswind – that have a significant impact on operating efficiency, and potentially the safety of operation. Together with wind-tunnel experiments performed in parallel – validated by this real-world data – recommendations for aerodynamic optimization can be made for freight-train and infrastructure operators and manufacturers.

Keywords: freight, aerodynamics, drag, crosswind stability, safety

Introduction

Aerodynamic resistance, drag, is a primary component of the overall resistance to motion a freight train experiences and therefore very important for energy efficiency. Aerodynamics becomes more important with train speed, so the plans and predictions of operating from 110 to 160 km/h and faster will only increase this importance. Depending on the type of power supply, this affects directly either emissions, or range – both of which are important considerations for current and future freight operation. In addition to drag, crosswind stability – and the resulting risk of overturning – as well as specific interaction with infrastructure like tunnels and bridges and other vehicles, makes freight aerodynamics also important for safety of operation.

Freight-trains operate in a variety of complex conditions that have a strong impact on the aerodynamic characteristics of efficiency and safety; weather, infrastructure and other vehicles - all with various locomotive, wagon and container configurations. It is important therefore, that any recommendations for aerodynamic optimization are based in the reality of such operation, and not solely in idealized conditions. To characterize the real-world aerodynamics, measurements have been performed on a full-scale shipping container, the DLR FR8-LAB, that has been transported on normal operating freight-trains in Europe. The FR8-LAB is a 'swap-body' shipping-container (Fig 1a) fitted with aerodynamic measurement equipment, that can be loaded in different configurations [1]. The FR8-LAB is self-contained, with an on-board solar-power supply, data-acquisition system and remote-access communication.

This work aims for improved freight-train operational efficiency and safety, through realizable aerodynamic optimization of: freight-train and wagon geometry, loading configuration schemes and infrastructure-vehicle and vehicle-vehicle interaction. Realizable optimization is enabled – and continuously supported and informed from improved understanding of causal flow physics – through the coupling of the real-world measurements from the FR8-LAB that validate state-of-the-art, controlled, scientific wind-tunnel optimization experiments.

Methodology

Real-world : DLR FR8-LAB

A bespoke IoT-based data acquisition system was developed for the FR8-LAB to ensure robust and energy efficient operation in the challenging industrial environment. Time-resolved (up to 1000Hz) surface-pressure measurements are performed at 330 positions on the container (Fig 1b). The reference side of the differential pressure-transducers is open to the interior pressure of the container. Pressure on the front and rear surface is integrated to provide insight into the pressure drag. Longitudinal rows and rings along the side and roof of the container estimate the side force, yaw and roll moments. The pressure measurements locations are selected to resolve the pressure gradients across the surface, and identify the transient pressure signatures of complex turbulent flow structures like the recirculation regions in between containers and flow separation at the roof/sides. This enables accurate predictions of the forces and moments on the container and provides insight into the underlying causal flow physics.

The container's operating conditions are measured by additional sensors (Fig 1c). These conditions are then associated to the measured surface-pressure and corresponding aerodynamic characteristics. A global navigation satellite system (GNSS) determines the location and the velocity over ground (VoG). Seven, single-point LiDAR distance sensors with ~40m range are located on the container's sides, roof and front/rear surface to quantitatively characterize the physical environment at high temporal resolution sampling rates of up to 1000Hz. Two additional LiDAR sensors point at the ground, and are also used to determine VoG. Two wide-angle 75° field-of-view (FoV) thermal cameras (able to operate at night and in poor weather conditions) provide additional qualitative information on the local topography. Accelerometers, barometric pressure and temperature sensors measure the conditions inside the container.

Figure 1: a. The DLR FR8-LAB loaded onto a wagon in an operational freight-train consist. b. The location of surface-pressure measurements. c. Environmental sensors: 7 x LiDAR (red), 2 x LiDAR VOG (orange), 2 x thermal cameras (green) and accelerometers (purple).

Wind-tunnel

The experimental investigation of different loading configurations was performed in the crosswind simulation facility Göttingen (SWG). The wind tunnel was set-up for a Reynolds number of 5.5×10^5 in relation to the test container width, corresponding to an inflow velocity of ~ 50 m/s. Figure 2 shows the 1:15 scaled freight train model, consisting of an up-/downstream flow body and a modifiable gap test section around a test container on a highly simplified freight wagon base, placed on a generic single track with ballast and rail. The test container corresponds to a scaled model of the DLR's FR8-LAB, mounted on a six-component strain-gauge balance onto the freight wagon base to provide a decoupled measurement of the aerodynamic drag force. Furthermore, the test container was equipped with 254 pressure taps to investigate the flow development around the container. In the initial study with incremental change of the gap sizes [3,4], the modifiable sections were filled with different sized blocks in order to vary the loading gaps up- and downstream. The filler part length corresponded to increments of the test container length, providing full-scale gaps of 0.156m up to 19.55m respectively 0.02 up to 2.5 times the container length.

The wind tunnel setup was modified to use attachable boundary layer argumentation devices on the upstream flow body in the red circled section indicated in Figure 2. The two different boundary layer argumentation configurations, BLA1 & BLA2, are shown in Figure 3b, c compared to the clean configuration shown in Figure 3. In both configurations about 2m of the upstream flow body sides and top starting at about 450mm flow body length were covered in roughness plates with more than 460 LEGO® 1x1 blocks + flat tile with dimensions of 8mm x 8mm base size and 10mm height. Additionally, a band of spikes was attached in front of the roughness plates. The size and spacing is the main difference between the two BLA-configurations: BLA1 spikes were 62mm long, 14mm base width, 32mm spacing; BLA2 spikes were 130mm long, 15mm base width, 48mm spacing.

Figure 2: Wind tunnel setup of a generic freight train model in the Crosswind Simulation Facility Göttingen with variable, front/rear loading gap sizes and addable boundary layer argumentation.

Figure 3: a) Generic freight train model installed in the SWG test-section, b) with boundary layer argumentation configuration BLA1 (LEGO®+spikes) and c) configuration BLA2 (LEGO®+larger spikes)

Results

Characterization of Real-world Operation

The average surface-pressure distribution measured during an example measurement (Fig 4) show high pressure at the front surface of the FR8-LAB and low pressure at the roof and side front edges caused by stagnated and separated flow respectively. The measured pressure on the surfaces of the container are integrated to estimate the global aerodynamic forces and moments acting on the container (illustrated in Fig 4b). The potential operational envelope of global forces, and thus efficiency and safety can then be mapped for many possible conditions. One such example, is the effect loading configuration has on efficiency.

Figure 4: a. Surface pressure distribution overlaid on the real FR8-LAB and the corresponding b. Resulting local and global force vectors and moments.

The surface pressure distributions (mean and standard deviation) and probability distribution of aerodynamic drag for a number of example cases with different loading configurations are presented in Figure 5 and 6 respectively. The local loading configurations presented corresponds to gaps either side of the container from 1.6 to >30m; ranging from the typical gap between containers on different wagons to gaps the size of multiple containers. Clear differences in the mean and fluctuating surface pressure are observable for different loading configurations. At the smallest gap, the entire front surface doesn't experience high pressure, only the upper and outer edges, and negligible separation and low pressure exists on the side and top edges. For the larger gaps the distribution is the same as the example in Figure 4, whilst the magnitude of the pressure increases with increasing gap. At the largest gap, the entire front surface sees high fluctuations, rather than just the edges. The aerodynamic drag coefficient also varies significantly with loading configuration, with means of $c_D = 0.17$ to 0.4 (>100% increase) with corresponding increasing standard deviations of $\sigma_{c_D} = 0.04$ - 0.13 .

Similar sensitivity of aerodynamic drag to freight-train loading configuration have previously been observed in field-tests [2], wind-tunnel experiments [3,4] and numerical simulations [5]. The examples presented are in 'clean' operating condition; no significant infrastructure interaction such as tunnels, large bridges or exposure to crosswind are included. Further, in these examples presented, the FR8-LAB was loaded in the approximate middle of the train consist (situated away from any local effects from the start and end of the train). Such operating conditions have already been observed to have significant effects on the aerodynamic loads, in addition to the loading configuration – these effects, as well as side-force and rolling moments are important for safety of operation. These results demonstrate that part of the aerodynamic operational envelope for real-world freight-trains have successfully been mapped.

Figure 5: Mean surface-pressure distributions from a. front and b. rear views, and standard deviation of surface-pressure c. front and d. rear views respectively for four example ‘clean’ measurements (no apparent crosswind, or infrastructure, vehicle interaction) with increasing front gap distances. Example #1 front gap $fG=1.62$, rear gap $rG=8.6m$, #2: $fG=8.6$, $rG=1.6m$, #3: $fG=14.76$, $rG=1.65m$, #4: $fG>30m$, $rG=14m$.

Figure 6: Density distribution of aerodynamic drag, c_D , of four example measurements with increasing front gap distances. Example #1 front gap $fG=1.62$, rear gap $rG=8.6m$, #2: $fG=8.6$, $rG=1.6m$, #3: $fG=14.76$, $rG=1.65m$, #4: $fG>30m$, $rG=14m$.

Figure 7: Drag of the test container from FR8-LAB field tests (Full-Scale) compared to wind tunnel experiments (WT) with same gap configurations (cases) as well as incremental gaps in front/rear (incr. GF/GR) and symmetric gaps without and with

boundary layer augmentation BLA1 and BLA2,

Wind-Tunnel Results

There is a variety of possible loading scheme gaps in real-world operation depending on spigot positions, buffer length, wagon length etc. An incremental drag study was performed to build up a drag database to use in an energy/cost savings calculation tool.

The measured drag curves from an incremental study into the sensitivity of drag to up- and downstream gap size (solid blue GF, and green GR lines) are plotted in Figure 6. Here, either the front or rear gap was incrementally changed, while the other kept fixed at 0.78m. In general, a clear increase in aerodynamic drag is visible for increasing gap size, with relative minor sensitivity for front gaps less than 2m and rear gaps less than 5m. Both gaps show a tendency of approaching "maxxing out", approaching a maximum drag, as the container approaches full isolation. Finer details of different drag regimes and their corresponding flow structures are discussed in [3] and [4] respectively.

Validation

Three specific different gap configurations from the FR8-LAB measurements were compared with wind tunnel experiment: case #1 with 1.62m front/ 8.61m rear gap; case #2 with 8.68m front/ 1.62m rear gap and case #3 with 14.76m front/ 1.65m rear gap. The ~1.6m gap corresponds to a typical inter-car gap, the ~8.6m gap an empty slot on a wagon and the ~14.7m gap e.g. an (large) empty slot with inter-car gap. The drag (Figure 6) is similar for case #1 with $c_D \sim 0.17$. Whilst for cases #2 and #3, the Full-Scale drag values were significantly lower than Wind-Tunnel by ~55% for case #2 (c_D of 0.2 to 0.44) and by 47% for case #3 (c_D of 0.3 to 0.56). Such difference between wind tunnel experiment and field tests have also been previously noted in other freight-train aerodynamic investigations [2]. The primary cause of difference is proposed to be due to the relatively 'clean' nature of the flow around the simplified train model in the wind-tunnel experiment, compared to the real-world complex messiness of the FR8-LAB measurements.

A first attempt to increase the accuracy in which the wind-tunnel represents real-world operation, is to artificially roughen the train model. To do this, the boundary layer on the roof and sides were augmented, with spires and roughness of two levels BLA1, and BLA2 applied. Only basic loading configurations were tested: six symmetric (front=rear; GF=GR) gap configurations: 0.8m, 1.9m, 2.8m, 7.8m, 15.6m and 19.5m. The drag for different loading configurations without boundary-layer-augmentation (BLA) (orange) and with BLA1 (red) or BLA2 (purple) are plotted in Figure 6 as function of the symmetric loading gap cases. The augmented results show the same trends as un-augmented, albeit with 25-35% lower with BLA1 and 30-40% lower with BLA2; closer to the real-world measurements of the FR8-LAB.

In Figure 7, the time-averaged surface-pressure distribution of the FR8-LAB and wind-tunnel with three boundary layer levels are presented with the closest comparable loading configurations tested. The same characteristic pressure distribution is visible for all cases: high pressure on the front and low-pressure regions in the front corners and on the sides due to flow separation. In particular, the non-uniform distribution on the front surface in case #1 is clearly evident in the FR8-LAB and WT results. These results confirm that the underlying flow physics are comparable: the container is experiencing similar flow structures and corresponding 3D pressure distribution, potentially only the magnitude (hence the absolute drag) is different. Further, the similarity of the 3 different BLA cases show that a messier train with larger boundary layer ahead of the container, effects the drag and reduces the overall pressure distribution magnitude, but doesn't change the overall distribution shape. Thus, the application of boundary layer roughness seems a promising method for improving the real-world representation in a wind-tunnel experiment;

the drag is closer to real-world, and no irregular changes to the pressure distribution occur.

Figure 7: surface pressure coefficient distributions from FR8-LAB and WT for difference comparable loading configuration cases.

Energy Savings Tool

A calculation tool was developed based off the wind-tunnel measurements calculate the difference in cumulative drag of a loading scheme derived from the different drag values of each single container. It can then be used to estimate the energy and cost saving potential [3]. Figure 8 shows an example process of estimating the difference in energy consumption between trains with different loading schemes (LS): a close-packed freight train (LS1), three empty slots (LS2), mixed wagon types & scattered load (LS3) and worst-case with one container per 3-slot wagon (LS4). A generic track speed profile was used with a 300km freight route and different train speed profiles of 30km/h to a max speed of 120km/h, 160km/h or 200km/h. Based on the drag database, the cumulative drag coefficient of the load increases by $\Delta c_D \sim 1.62/5.81/15.25$ for LS2/3/4 respectively, which corresponds to an estimated additional energy consumption of 0.6/2.0/5.2MWh at 120km/h and significantly greater of 1.3/4.8/12.6MWh at 200km/h corresponding to 195/720/1890€ at 0.15€/kWh (Buhr et al., 2024). These estimations are based on the drag database without boundary layer argumentation. With advanced, more realistic wind tunnel experiments the accuracy of the estimation tool will be improved.

Figure 8: a) Four example loading schemes of a 660 m long freight train loaded with 24 containers, b) example of train speed track profile with c) estimated energy and cost savings potential

Conclusion

An in-depth experimental campaign investigating operational freight-train aerodynamics has been performed – consisting of on-rail measurements on the European rail network and a state-of-the-art wind-tunnel experiment performed in parallel. Results have indicated significant differences in aerodynamic characteristics based on the operating conditions of freight trains: loading configuration, and infrastructure interaction – that can have a significant impact on operating efficiency, and potentially safety of operation. The wind-tunnel experiments enabled loading configuration to be investigated in detail. The full-scale results have been used to validate this methodology. Comparison shows the same trends and flow physics. However, a difference in absolute aerodynamic resistance (drag) has been observed, as in other previous research. An improved methodology has been tested, adding roughness ahead of the test container, in the form of boundary-layer augmentation. This method has shown promise, bringing the comparison between full scale and wind-tunnel closer, whilst keeping the comparable flow physics consistent. An energy savings tool has been developed from this work, using the aerodynamics to predict energy efficiency and subsequently operational cost for train operators. This tool being the first of planned recommendations for optimized freight-train aerodynamics in real-world operation.

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